

**LEARNING EXPERIENCES AND OUTCOMES OF VALUES EDUCATION
TEACHERS AT WESTERN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY
(WMSU): INCULCATION APPROACH**

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Learning Experiences and Outcomes of Values Education Teachers at Western Mindanao State University (WMSU): Incultation Approach

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Abstract

This study employed qualitative research, applying a phenomenological approach to determine the experiences of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) teachers utilizing the incultation approach as well as the learning outcomes attained by the students. This study made use of one-on-one interviews with ten (10) secondary teachers who teach Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) or Values Education, as well as those who employ the incultation approach at Western Mindanao State University's (WMSU) Integrated Laboratory School (ILS) in Zamboanga City, Philippines. The study revealed that teachers defined the incultation approach as instilling values and students following instructions. Teachers have been utilizing it in their EsP classes, and there were no difficulties encountered by the teachers and they can conceivably integrate the incultation approach to the EsP concepts in their distinctive way: making reference to the topic of the student's life experiences, giving examples, and constantly instructing and reminding students. The learning outcomes are achieved by the students and can be demonstrated through the assessments or evaluation, through students' active participation, and if students' exhibit good behavior by applying and practicing values that have been instilled in them.

Keywords: *Incultation, Values Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, ESP teachers, learning outcomes*

Introduction

Values Education goal is to instill the core values: Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan, and Makabansa among the learners at all educational levels in order to develop an individual become committed in a just and humane society and an independent and democratic nation (Gulapa, n.d.).

In order to deliver concepts in values effectively, teachers used various teaching approaches: the incultation approach, the moral development approach, the value clarification approach, the analysis approach, and others. Teachers of values education have always incorporated the incultation approach as their primary teaching method as many believe that it is an effective way to impart values (Edaño & Meer, 2021).

According to Reyes (2019) incultation approach is used as a teaching strategy to internalize a predetermined set of values to the students. Thus, students have to simply comply with the teachers' instructions. The most commonly used strategies in incultation approach are modeling, positive and negative reinforcement, mocking, and story-telling.

However, another study has also indicated that the incultation approach has been notably unsuccessful (Chaitanya, 2017). There are only limited studies that were conducted on incultation approach as a teaching strategy. According to the study of Edaño and Meer (2021), Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) teachers in Zambales, chose incultation approach as one of the most commonly used and effective approach among other approaches in values education.

However, it was not able to clarify why incultation approach is successful aside from the students' overall grade in EsP and why teachers favor it as a strategy of instructing edukasyon sa pagpapakatao because Thakar (2020) stated that the value clarification is the most influential approach. Apart from this, not many studies were able to determine what common techniques and strategies EsP teachers use to make incultation approach more effective to the learners, especially in imparting good values to the students.

Hence, this research study aimed to provide the lived experiences of EsP teachers in utilizing the incultation approach as a teaching strategy, to give more detailed information as to what other learning outcomes students can attain upon the implementation of the incultation approach.

Thus, there is a need to perceive and find out what common techniques does EsP teachers use while utilizing the incultation approach, aside from the commonly used strategies; are there any more strategies that would make learners acquire good values, so that they can be able to apply in their daily lives.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the experiences of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) teachers utilizing incultation approach, as well as the learning outcomes attained by the students. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of EsP teachers in implementing incultation approach in teaching Values Education?
2. How learning outcomes are achieved by the students in using incultation approach in Values Education?

Literature Review

Inculcation Approach

The inculcation approach is a teaching strategy that aims to assist students in internalizing a particular set of values, according to Reyes (2019). The most prevalent methods in the inculcation approach are modeling, positive and negative reinforcement, narrative, and mocking. Additionally, Sobredo (2016) writes in inculcation approach teachers typically dictate to students what they are supposed to perceive and how they ought to act.

In contradiction, inculcation of values occurs through allowing students to actively participate in class by giving them activities, examples, and stories that will enable them to relate and share their experiences and become more engaged in class (Piyasa, n.d).

When students relate to the topic and are given real life problems or examples and through the experiences that students share and the ways on how teachers apply the lesson itself to their everyday lives, these techniques aid the teachers in comprehending the perspectives of their students (Alcantara, 2019).

Importance of Value Inculcation

Saravanan (2019) Inculcation approach ingrain and incorporate values and standards that are imposed by society to the learners. Thus, it is important to teach and encourage learners to uphold values rather than holding back from doing it and undermine them. It is also said that inculcating values is the responsibility of the family, school, and community so that they can live better lives and in doing so it is necessary that pre-specified values are intentionally cultivated in their minds.

Correspondingly, according to Babatunde et al. (2021) Inculcation approach instil fundamental values to the learners that underpin society, which helps convert possible negative values into positive ones that will allow the learners to display advisable social behavior. Thus, having a teaching methods and techniques in the implementation of inculcation approach will help the learners clarify and identify their own set of values.

Roles in Value Inculcation

According to Rekha and Deepa (2019), the foundation of a decent society is the students since today's students are tomorrow's leaders. If we manage to raise good individuals, we can establish a healthy society. A teacher's main purpose should be inculcating values in their student and teachers should function as role examples to students in schools.

Further, even if it requires a lifetime's worth of work, Banerjee et al. (2016) emphasize that it is essential to inculcate the proper values in students during their years at school. Teachers greatly influence how students construct their values due to teachers' character, deeds, and activities preferences.

However, teaching the values by themselves won't have much impact. Teachers should live in a way that sets an example for their students by practicing the values they promote. When teachers live out the values they inculcate, students acquire them as they recreate what they observe in their teachers. Teachers should also employ a variety of tactics and guidelines so that students may conveniently understand and embrace the values being instilled (Bhutani et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a phenomenological qualitative research design to perceive the experiences of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) teachers towards utilizing the inculcation approach as a teaching strategy in delivering concepts in ESP. Phenomenological method of qualitative study emphasized the similarities and as well as difference among the selected people who share the same experiences. To arrive at a description of the nature of the specific situation is the methods' primary goal (Creswell, 2013).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were secondary education teachers in the Integrated Laboratory School (ILS) of Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) that teaches Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP) or Values Education in Zamboanga City, Philippines. There were a total of ten (10) respondents who took part in the one-on-one interview. Hence, the sample that was employed is the purposive sampling technique.

This study employed a qualitative research method to thoroughly explore the experiences of the EsP teachers that implement the inculcation approach to teach the concepts of EsP, and the learning outcomes gained by the students upon the application of the inculcation approach.

To gather the data, ten (10) EsP teachers who teach values education that used an inculcation approach in the Integrated Laboratory School (ILS) of Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) in Zamboanga City, were interviewed one-on-one. Before the interview, a letter requesting approval to carry out the study was handed to the dean of the College of Teacher Education and the principal of the Integrated Laboratory School (ILS). The researchers then obtained the respondents' permission before interviewing them, and they

were made aware of the benefits, risks, and confidentiality of their responses. In order to collect the data, the researchers asked six (6) questions during the interview. The evaluation of the research's findings, conclusions, and recommendations occurred after the data had been collected.

Instrument

Semi-structured interview questions were employed as a research instrument in this study. The research instrument included questions that answered the research's aim of finding out the experiences of EsP teachers that practice the inculcation approach, the teaching techniques that they apply in delivering EsP concepts while utilizing the inculcation approach, as well as the learning outcomes the students attain.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the ten (10) respondents was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly. To interpret the data gathered, this study made use of thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method for analysing qualitative data to find recurring topics, notions, patterns, etc. (Caulfield, 2022).

Ethical Considerations

The study was carried out in conformity with fundamental ethical standards for research. When processing the subject material, the researchers guaranteed complete confidentiality. Participants can rest assured knowing that their personal information is safeguarded, protected, and kept out of the hands of third parties. Without the participants' permission, no data-collecting activities, including capturing pictures, videos, or voice recordings, were carried out. In order to prevent physical or mental harm to the respondents both during and after the interview, the researchers took the necessary precautions. The study's identity and outcomes were maintained by the researchers in a framework of accurate observational anonymity.

The researchers were aware of the participants' flexibility to respond and make choices based on their experiences, values, and viewpoints; they were also given the autonomy to express themselves. The participants have full access to the reports and research findings, and the researchers made sure that the results are totally honest and accurately reflect the results.

Results and Discussion

This section entails respondent demographic data, and data analysis, which include data management, a summary of data collected, and presentation of emerging themes and codes from respondents' responses.

Table 1. Demographic Data of the Respondents

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Area of Specialization</i>	<i>Years of teaching Values Education</i>
Participant 1	Male	Economics	2 years
Participant 2	Male	English	10 years
Participant 3	Female	Filipino	7 years
Participant 4	Female	Science	1 year
Participant 5	Female	Filipino	5 years
Participant 6	Female	Physical Science	3 years
Participant 7	Male	Values Education	5 years
Participant 8	Female	MAPEH	3 years
Participant 9	Female	Filipino	1 year
Participant 10	Female	English	Half a year

The table above contains the summary of the respondents' demographic data. All respondents are educators. Three teachers are male and seven are female. They vary in terms of the area of specialization, with three major in Filipino, two major in English, and the rest major in Economics, Science, Physical Science, Values, and MAPEH. One has ten years of experience teaching Values Education, one has seven years, two have five years, two have three years, two have one year, and one has less than a year of teaching Values Education.

The obtained data were subjected to a number of analytic procedures, which comprised diverse techniques such as open coding, theme emerging, and the interpretation of data. The data were synthesized during the open coding, and were direct, comprehensible, and extensive enough to identify patterns and themes. The emerging theme highlighted elements illuminating close connections between codes and themes where we can interpret and make sense of the data. The interpretation of the data was the last step of the process; it generated all the main ideas necessary to address the research question.

There were several questions asked during the in-depth one-on-one interview to determine the experiences of EsP teachers when utilizing inculcation approach. Three (3) themes emerged from the teachers' responses to Research Question 1:

1. Teachers defined and employed the inculcation approach in values education.
2. Teachers integrate the inculcation approach into their values education classes.
3. The inculcation approach was not difficult for teachers to implement.

Table 2. *Themes and Codes*

<i>Superordinate Theme</i>	<i>Subordinate Theme</i>	<i>Coding</i>
Experiences of EsP teachers in implementing inculcation approach in teaching Values Education.	The Definition and Employment of Inculcation Approach	Instilling values Learners following instruction Frequently utilized
	Integration of Inculcation Approach in Values Education	Relating to students' experiences By giving examples Instructing and reminding Convenience to employ
Learning outcomes achieved by the students in using inculcation approach in Values Education.	Teachers' experiences with the inculcation approach	
	Learning outcomes Students' Active Participation	Recitation Engagement Sharing of Experiences
	Students' Behaviors	Application of values Active Participation
	Assessments conducted by teachers	Performance Task (e.g., role play) Situational Quizzes Behavior

The Definition and Employment of Inculcation Approach

The majority of teacher-respondents defined and asserted that they utilize the inculcation approach in teaching EsP concepts. Their definition of inculcation encompasses instilling values and having students follow instructions. The Inculcation Approach entails instilling in students' minds the values and standards desired by society (Saravanan, 2019). In addition, students are typically passive learners in the inculcation approach; they are expected to follow the teachers' instructions regarding what they are supposed to comprehend and how they are supposed to act (Sobredo, 2016).

Integration of Inculcation Approach in Values Education

The teacher-respondents have integrated the inculcation approach in their values education classes in a variety of ways, including relating to students' experiences, providing examples, instructing and reminding them. In inculcation approach, teachers should present a moral dilemma to students so that they can relate it to their own experiences and current events (Erbas and Baskurt, 2020). More so, learners are expected to be passive recipients of knowledge in the inculcation approach, to simply follow teachers' instructions, respond to their questions, and change their behavior (Teachmint, n.d.).

Teachers' experiences with the inculcation approach

The teacher-respondents have asserted that they have not encounter difficulties when they employ inculcation approach, so they utilize it most of the time in their EsP classes. Values Education teachers in Zambales chose the inculcation approach to employ in their classroom because they believe it is the most effective (Edaño & Meer, 2021).

There were several questions asked during the in-depth one-on-one interview to determine the learning outcomes achieved by the students in using inculcation approach. Three (3) themes emerged from the teachers' responses to Research Question 2:

1. Learning outcomes are achieved when teachers see students' active participation.
2. Learning outcomes are achieved when teachers see students' behavior.
3. Learning outcomes are achieved when teachers conduct assessments.

Students' Active Participation

The majority of teachers stated that students actively participate and are engaged in class, especially when they can relate to the topic and are given real-life problems, examples and situations. Piyasa (n.d.), states that inculcation of values occurs through allowing students to actively participate in class by giving them activities, examples, and stories that will enable them to relate and share their experiences and become more engaged.

Students' Behavior

According to the teacher respondents, students' behavior is an important part of achieving learning outcomes and feedback because it allows them to see that the students are actively participating and applying the values that have been taught or instilled in them. It was stated by the teacher respondents: that whenever they see students displaying negative behavior, they try to modify it by drawing their attention to them and according to the theory of Skinner he believed that people learn the most depending on the outcomes of their actions (McLeod, 2018).

Assessments Conducted by Teachers'

The majority of the respondents stated that they were able to achieve the learning outcomes. Thus, the majority of them give assessment,

evaluation, and performance tasks, as well as checking on their behavior to see whether they were able to apply and practice good values, and use the results of these assessments as one of the evidences to determine whether these students met the learning outcomes. Sahikayasi and Kelleci (2013), found out that teachers regularly assess the learners whether they have already obtained the values or not through the use of observation approach.

Conclusions

The findings of this study suggest that regardless of the areas of expertise of the teachers, majority were able to define the inculcation approach when inquired; instilling values, students following the teacher's instruction, students being passive learners when the inculcation approach is employed, and teachers being the role model of the values that they inculcate. The researchers concluded that since students look up to and are expected to obey teachers, it is essential that teachers must act as role models and/or live by the values that they teach to students.

In terms of incorporating the inculcation approach into the teaching of EsP concepts, the teacher-respondents integrate it through making reference to the topic of the students' life experiences, make the students aware of the consequences of their actions if they made a poor decision, by giving examples, and teachers constantly instruct and remind students of the values that they must practice. Additionally, teachers constantly instruct and remind students of the values that they must practice so that it can be gradually applied and instilled in the student's mind. Although the inculcation approach is typically thought of as teachers giving students instructions that they must follow, the researchers believe there are various ways to involve the student in the process of acquiring the values as the inculcation approach can be incorporated in different ways.

When it comes to difficulties encountered, the teacher-respondents reported no difficulties because it can simply be related to the students' experiences, as well as the students already having the values. Therefore, the inculcation approach proves to be convenient to use.

In addition, when the inculcation approach is utilized, the teachers observed that the students participate actively in class when they inculcate values by giving examples and presenting them with scenarios, situations, or real-life problems. Therefore, the researchers conclude that by giving these students problem-based examples and situations, they will further deepen their understanding of their actions as they identify the problems and situations given in the examples.

Moreover, it is important that the teachers will call their attention and make them aware of what they did wrong and how their actions affect them now and in the future. In this case, the researchers conclude that when students are displaying negative behaviors the teachers must intervene straight away to make sure that the learners will realize that what they are doing is wrong and that will be consequences for that action.

Furthermore, when it comes to students' feedback when the inculcation approach is being employed. Teachers consider students' behavior, performance, and application and/or practicing good values as feedback to see if the class enjoys the inculcation approach and if the students have really attained the learning outcomes. Given these points, the researchers believe that teachers can utilize different types of assessment to determine if the approach is being enjoyed and is effective for the students. Teachers can also assess the student's behavior to see if they are able to exhibit or show the values that have been instilled in them.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are presented concerning any organization and individuals:

The researchers recommend that school administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders ensure that high-quality teaching strategies are being used in values education. Additionally, EsP teachers are encouraged to explore and utilize different teaching approaches such as the inculcation approach, to promote excellence in the teaching of values education and gain insights into the effectiveness of the approach regarding the learner's performance and behavior.

The researchers also recommend future researchers to use the findings of the study as a reference to provide them with additional insights on the use of the inculcation approach in teaching values education. For those researchers who wish to conduct to make a follow-up or similar study.

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